

Étude ma vie et la
pandémie au
Québec

METHODES

Methodological report

General information

November, 2nd 2020 Version

**« Ma vie avec la pandémie au Québec – MAVIPAN »
Living with the pandemic in Quebec – MAVIPAN**

Methodological document – General information

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www.mavipan.ca/partners

Version of November 2nd, 2020

Context

The *Living with the pandemic* (MAVIPAN - *Ma vie avec la pandémie*) study was launched as a collective effort brought together by the 4 research centers of the CIUSSS de la Capitale-Nationale, namely CIRRIS *Center for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation and Social Integration*, CRUJeF *University Research Center for Youth and Families*, CERVO research center, and VITAM *Centre de recherche en santé durable*, with the support of Université Laval's PULSAR collaborative research platform.

It is intended to be an initiative designed to support the research community and serve as a public health information tool.

MAVIPAN is supported by a group of researchers, partners, and collaborators. The complete list is available on MAVIPAN's website at www.mavipan.ca

Caution

This methodological document was written for MAVIPAN's researchers and collaborators. It is made available before the end of the study, while several data collections are ongoing or planned. The information provided in this document is subject to change pending study progress. Updated versions will be released periodically in the coming months and years. If you have any questions or concerns regarding the information in this document, we suggest you contact the study's team at mavipan.ciusscn@ssss.gouv.qc.ca

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. BACKGROUND	5
2. OBJECTIVES OF MAVIPAN	7
2.1 Conceptual groundwork	7
3. METHODS	8
3.1 Study design	8
3.2 Targeted population	8
3.3 Recruitment and sampling	10
3.4 Data collection and measures	12
3.5 Ethics	14
3.6 Analyses	14
3.7 Research transparency and data sharing	15
4. GOVERNANCE	15
4.1 Contacts	15
5. REFERENCES	16
ANNEXE 1	20
ANNEXE 2	21
ANNEXE 3	26

1. BACKGROUND

The health crisis resulting from COVID-19 is causing a major worldwide social reorganization that will have profound consequences on our society.¹ Affected countries have attempted to contain the spread of the virus by imposing extraordinary isolation efforts on their population.^{2,3} One-third of the world's population (~3 billion individuals) has, is or will experience some kind of isolation measure, causing an unprecedented and rapidly evolving psychosocial crisis.⁴⁻⁷ While biomedical research is relentlessly pursuing its efforts to understand the impact of the disease on infected individuals and develop new treatments and vaccines, the psychosocial consequences that could permanently affect our well-being, the state of our health system, and our society cannot be ignored.^{4,8-10}

Failure to address psychosocial and health issues will prolong the impact of the pandemic for years to come. The psychosocial consequences of this health crisis will spare no one, particularly vulnerable individuals, and will persist long after restrictions are lifted and the pandemic is over.^{4,10-12} The combination of professional changes, “risk” classification, possible loss of employment, resulting economic difficulties, changes in relationship dynamics between partners and family dynamics, school closures and reduction of services in health and social services network may all have an impact on the adjustment and development of individuals of all ages.¹³⁻¹⁷ This impact will be significant for individuals facing unique contexts or challenges (e.g., the elderly, individuals living with a disability, individuals with a chronic or mental health condition, underprivileged families) and will most likely exacerbate existing social, racial and gender inequalities in health and human development.¹⁸⁻²⁵

The magnitude of the current COVID-19 response has destabilized several aspects of our health and social services structures. Health and social services workers are experiencing major changes in their practice during this crisis.^{10,26} Services are being suspended, others maintained or intensified, and new intervention strategies are rapidly being adopted to adjust to lockdown measures or risk of virus transmission.^{27,28} Service interruptions have an impact on the physical and mental health and subsequent development of the most vulnerable individuals specifically.²⁹ Many of the workers bear constant witness to the human toll of the pandemic and, all too often, become part of it.^{10,30,31} Further, this occurs in a context where they are subject to the same measures as the rest of the population, thus placing greater demands on their ability to adapt.³¹⁻³³ It is crucial to document practice changes and adjustments of these individuals, who must remain available for their families, colleagues and the population.

Recovering from the pandemic will require a social and economic response that is just as important as the current efforts to minimize the spread of infection.^{1,34} There is an urgent need for information on the evolution of the psychosocial dimensions of health and coping strategies used by our population and our health and social services structures. By comprehensively documenting such information, stakeholders will be in a better position to make timely informed decisions and implement strategies to minimize the expected consequences of the crisis on our mental health and well-being.

The MAVIPAN (*Ma vie avec la pandémie*) cohort was developed in response to these individual and collective needs. It was born out of an unprecedented collective effort between the four research centers of the Quebec Integrated University Health & Social Services Center (CIUSSS) of the Capitale-Nationale and their province-wide academic, governmental, institutional and community partners.

2. OBJECTIVES OF MAVIPAN

Overall, this research project will allow: (i) in the short-term, to support establishments of the health and social services network in deploying and organizing services in times of crisis and in the recovery period, and (ii) in the medium- and long-term, to thoroughly document the impacts of the crisis and coping strategies at the individual, family, community and health and social services system levels to respond adequately to similar crises that may occur in the future.

More specifically, this research project aims to document, monitor, and analyze, based on the evolution of the health crisis:

- The adaptation of individuals and families, particularly those in vulnerable situations;
- The adaptation of actors in the health and social services sector;
- The adaptation of service structures;
- Social and professional organization.

This research project is based on the expertise and complementary experience of researchers and stakeholders (citizens, health and social services professionals, managers, community organizations) relative to all psychosocial and health dimensions of individuals. Together they provide the ability to approach this project from an interdisciplinary and intersectoral perspective, from a social responsibility and sustainable health angle.

2.1 Conceptual groundwork

MAVIPAN is based on (i) the integrated Knowledge Translation (iKT) approach that actively involves knowledge users (KUs) throughout the entire research process and its governance to enhance the relevance and uptake of results, and on (ii) the complementary framework Strategy for Patient-Oriented Research (SPOR) to foster a climate in which researchers and stakeholders understand the value of patient involvement.

Further, MAVIPAN's design, measures, and analyses are also informed by (i) the Model of Psychosocial Impact of Natural Disasters that specifically addresses coping mechanisms and mitigation strategies during traumatic events, and (ii) Dahlgren and Whitehead's Model of the Social Determinants of Health³⁵ that identifies the environmental, social, and individual factors that hinder or improve the health of individuals and create inequalities between populations.

3. METHODS

3.1 Study design

MAVIPAN is a five-year, “living” longitudinal observational cohort study targeting all territories in the province of Quebec.

The cohort’s “living” characteristic allows us to adapt the quantitative and qualitative measurements and their time points according to the needs identified by the populations of interest and the expected phases of the health crisis evolution.¹

These suggested phases, specifically by the National Institute of Public Health of Quebec (INSPQ), include: (i) **the impact phase**, (ii) **the turning point phase**, corresponding to the moment when the crisis is controlled by implemented measures; (iii) **the phase immediately after the crisis**, corresponding to the lifting of restrictive measures, and (iv) **the recovery phase** during the months or years following the return to "normal". We will also consider additional waves of infection and key events (e.g., vaccines) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Study design

3.2 Targeted population

The study targets the entire population of the province of Quebec. The general inclusion criteria are minimal: be 14 years old or over, read and understand French or English, and

¹ We are aware that this may lead to some changes to the project, and we are working in close collaboration with the Research Ethics Committee of the CIUSSS de la Capitale-Nationale to make all the necessary amendments.

agree to provide information (phone number or email) allowing for future contact as this is a longitudinal study.

3.2.1 Vulnerable, or considered to be vulnerable, populations

It is essential to have a high proportion of participants from generally vulnerable or considered vulnerable in the context of this health crisis, populations. We propose targeting the following populations:

Elderly: Our seniors are the most at risk in this health crisis. We are targeting the recruitment of people aged 65 and over, in different housing situations (e.g., CHSLD) or living independently at home.

People with disabilities: People with motor, language, hearing, intellectual or cognitive disabilities, and with autism spectrum disorder, as well as their caregivers are most vulnerable at this time due to changes in services offered to them, the limited capacity they may have to follow health recommendations, and their health risks.

Vulnerable youths and families: Young people aged 14-17 years old as well as families with young children (under six), single-parent or blended, and adults who have experienced a recent separation are targeted. We are also targeting families who are receiving social services at the primary (e.g., young pregnant women) or secondary (e.g., children monitored by child protection) levels. We are also able to obtain information regarding children of parents and caregivers who also participate in the cohort.

People with chronic diseases: We still know very little about the impact of the virus and changes to service structures on people with chronic diseases. Given the online nature of recruiting and filling of questionnaires, participants will self-report their diagnosed chronic disease(s).

People with mental disorders: The entire population is currently at risk of psychological consequences resulting from the health crisis. However, the impact may be even greater in those who already have a mental health disorder (self-reported) such as anxiety, mood, psychotic, or post-traumatic stress disorders.

Individuals belonging to ethnic minorities: Many immigrants have experienced war, isolation, refugee camps and many other crises. It is possible that these previous experiences have better prepared them to follow the restrictions implemented. It is also possible that these people already have strategies or resources to manage stress. They may, however, suffer from an additional psychosocial burden because of their immigrant or ethnic minority status or previous trauma.

Actors in the health and social services sectors: We target actors in the health and social services sectors, ranging from health professionals to facility managers, including support staff and attendants.

Rural areas: It is crucial to understand the repercussions that this crisis will have on access to service structures by rural communities and on the potential initiatives allowing actors in these areas to face this crisis in the absence of additional resources.

Indigenous people: We aim to work closely with various actors from Indigenous communities (e.g., Manawan, Wemotaci, Opitciwan, Wendake) to ensure that these populations are represented. However, links with the actors of these communities remain to be established.

3.3 Recruitment and sampling

MAVIPAN involves a non-probabilistic purposive sampling associated with online sampling and a snowballing technique without size restriction. Based on the recruitment rate thus far, we expect to recruit 5,000 participants by the end of 2021 and 7,500 participants by the end of the study.

We recognize biases and limitations associated with this approach (e.g., sampling error, lack of population representation). We have included key sociodemographic questions that will allow us to compare and weigh data according to provincial and national standards. We have used similar questions validated by key institutions such as Statistics Canada to further ensure the comparability of our findings.

Participant recruitment began during **the impact phase** (April 29th, 2020), which is when lockdown measures were most stringent. Participants are recruited through complementary approaches tailored to the populations of interest (see Table 1). The registration is continuously open and will continue throughout the study.

Table 1. Summary of recruitment methods

APPROACHES	TARGETED POPULATIONS	TOOLS AND CONTACT	RELEVANCE
Invitation to CIUSSS and CISSS users, health professionals, social services workers, administrative and managerial staff	Users Vulnerable groups Individuals with disabilities and requiring help to participate Actors in the health and social services sector Managers Patients with COVID-19	Contact by CIUSSS and CISSS staff Defined script to limit any undue pressure	Allows to target hard-to-reach people with special needs Allows to target actors in the health and social services sector Allows to reach patients with COVID-19
Media, social networks, and mailing lists	General population Population specific sector (e.g., Laval University, Quebec City employees)	Broadcast messages (link to the study Web page)	Quickness and ease of dissemination of the Web link Possibility to join participants outside the territory
Health workers and community organizations	Specific vulnerable groups	Contact by staff of CIUSSS, CISSS and collaborating organizations Defined script to limit any undue pressure or sharing of the broadcast message (link to the Web page)	Allows to target hard-to-reach people and those with special needs
Snowball method	General population Participants' loved ones	Project participants will have the opportunity to transfer the Web link to their entourage	Facilitates the recruitment of the general population and vulnerable loved ones of project participants
External cohorts	Vulnerable groups	If the ethical certificates allow it, researchers will be able to distribute the Web link to participants of other studies	Will allow to target vulnerable population groups

3.3.1 Participant retention plan

We recognize the challenge of loss to follow-up in potential cohorts. We have developed a retention plan that includes, but is not limited to: study branding, targeted advertising, incentives (e.g. gift cards), personalized emails, periodical vulgarized summaries, disseminated results to the population, and a personalized study web page to keep participants informed and engaged.

3.4 Data collection and measures

We collect quantitative and qualitative data according to the following modalities:

3.4.1 Quantitative data collection

Quantitative data collection is done via online questionnaires using the REDCap electronic data acquisition platform that is managed by Pulsar (www.pulsar.ca). Registration, consent, and questionnaires can be completed on different digital devices, in French or English. We also provide support to those who do not have Internet or computer access, have limited digital literacy, or a disability to fill out the questionnaires.

Participants can register at any point over the course of the study and complete a thorough baseline questionnaire (30–45 min). Additional questionnaires, up to four per year, will be tailored to key events in the crisis evolution (e.g., second wave) and to changes in restrictive measures (e.g., school closures). These include a brief (15 min) and standardized follow-up questionnaire which we intend to administer at least twice a year and ad hoc questionnaires (<30 min) adjusted to key events (e.g., vaccines) (Figure 1).

A notice followed by one reminder is sent to participants when a new questionnaire becomes available. Participants are given a week to complete questionnaires (i.e., with the possibility of starting, stopping, and returning to the saved questionnaire later). Questionnaires have been and will continue to be developed and tested with key experts and stakeholders, using brief (instead of exhaustive) validated measures when available. Key dates regarding invitations to complete questionnaires are available in Appendix 1. Additional information can be found in the questionnaire section of the methodological document.

Whenever possible, we chose validated measures based on: our theoretical models, Public Health recommendations, and consensus from experts and stakeholders. We document health, social, behavioral, and individual determinants as well as the psychosocial impacts of the pandemic in the baseline and follow-up questionnaires (Figure 2). We have

specific measures and indicators for vulnerable populations, such as disease management, changes in life circumstances attributable to the pandemic, or caregiver burden. Participants can respond to open-ended questions addressing current or expected challenges, helpful innovations, moments of hope, and additional topics they wish to see addressed in future questionnaires.

Figure 2. Summary of measures

3.4.3 Authorization for future contact

When registering, we ask participants for their permission to contact them in the future for additional research activities. This will allow us to add ancillary protocols or amendments (e.g., interviews with subsets of participants) based on the evolution of the pandemic, our findings, and the needs of stakeholders, which will significantly improve the quality and relevance of the information collected. Likewise, this will link MAVIPAN with provincial, national, and international initiatives related to COVID-19, thus fostering dynamic and multidisciplinary collaborations leading to increased impact.

3.4.4 Qualitative data

Each protocol or qualitative amendment will be unique but will (i) share the common elements of its interview guide (e.g., mitigation strategies, pandemic impact) and (ii) be based on best practices for the conduct of its activities. We will conduct semi-structured interviews and focus groups primarily through secure online media (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams) for now and will adapt as the social distancing and restrictions are lifted. The duration and number of participants will be tailored to each research question. Additional approaches (e.g., observations) could be added if necessary. Additional information regarding the qualitative aspects will be available in a specific methodological document shortly.

3.5 Ethics

We have worked, and continue to work, closely with our Research Ethics Board, which has played a key role in the design of this "living" cohort. We have implemented models and procedures that allow for a fluid process and a rapid response (e.g., within days) to newly submitted questionnaires and supporting protocols. All study procedures were approved by the respective Research Ethics Boards of all participating institutions. This study is registered with Clinicaltrial.gov (NCT04575571).

3.6 Analyses

The analyses will be carried out according to the research questions. They may be transversal and longitudinal for quantitative data or thematic for qualitative data. Whenever possible, we will perform analyses using mixed methods, with both sequential and simultaneous analyses of quantitative and qualitative data, to strengthen our ability to answer our research questions. The results of the quantitative analyses will inform the steps of qualitative data collection and the hypotheses derived from the qualitative analyses will inform the composition of subsequent measurements. Triangulation will be used to corroborate our conclusions and help explain paradoxes or inconsistencies emerging from the qualitative or quantitative analyses.

Furthermore, throughout the study, we will conduct cross-comparisons between ancillary protocols (including a meta-analysis of all qualitative findings) which will contribute to a conceptual framework on health impact and coping strategies during a worldwide pandemic.

3.7 Research transparency and data sharing

The substantial investments required to carry out large studies and the unprecedented nature of this health crisis support the optimal use of MAVIPAN's data. Data will be shared in accordance with the joint statement from the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR) regarding data sharing and research findings related to this coronavirus pandemic. MAVIPAN's transparency will be highlighted by the accessibility to the datasets, codebooks and supporting documents.

Researchers and collaborators will be able to submit research questions and gain access to datasets. Questions under investigation will be posted on our website to avoid duplication and to promote collaboration among the researchers' community, healthcare establishments, public health organizations, government officials, and community organizations. The resulting publications will be open access.

A specific document on data access and the dissemination of results is available.

4. GOVERNANCE

We have established an equitable, inclusive, and sustainable governance plan that fully includes citizens, patients, other stakeholders, experts and representatives of participating research centers, health facilities and organizations across the province.

Thus, we have assembled:

(i) a Steering Committee (quarterly meetings) that provides strategic leadership, notably including priorities of research questions, milestones and national and international collaborations, and facilitates research and knowledge translation activities;

(ii) an Executive Committee (monthly meetings) that reviews requests for collaborations and submission of research questions (i.e., alignment with research priorities and feasibility), progress and challenges of ongoing work, approval of publications to be submitted, and the scholarship process for graduate students, and;

(iii) a coordination team (bi-weekly meetings) that will handle MAVIPAN's daily operations.

4.1 Contacts

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ANNEXE 1

MAVIPAN Calendar

DATE	STEPS
APRIL 29, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final initial ethics approval • Online posting of the Baseline phase 1 questionnaire in French
MAY 21, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical approval Amendment F1-6022 for the MHAVIE, the MQE and the complementary questions for people with disabilities • Ethical approval Amendment F1-6060 for the full English translation of the project • Integration of new questions to the baseline phase 1 questionnaire in French for participants registered as of this date at the end of the afternoon (ID over 1351 - first participant with disabilities to have access to the full questionnaire)
MAY 22, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online posting of the questionnaire in English (including the additional questions described above)
MAY 26, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants with a disability registered between April 29 and May 21 (participants whose ID is between 1 and 1351) invited to answer the new questions from CIRRIIS
JUNE 10, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical approval Amendment F1-6212 of the Follow-up 1 questionnaire
JUNE 18, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sending of invitations for the Follow-up 1 questionnaire (in French only)
JULY 15, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical approval Amendment F1-6348 Baseline phase 2 questionnaire
JULY 20, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pausing of registrations for the Baseline phase 1 questionnaire in French and English
JULY 30, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online posting of the Baseline phase 2 questionnaire in French and English
OCTOBER 21, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online posting of the Follow-up 2 questionnaire (bilingual)

ANNEXE 2

Calendar of lockdown measures

Evolution of the various measures related to the COVID-19 pandemic in Quebec

 = Montreal Metropolitan Community (MMC)

 = Other specific regions of Quebec

Chronological order for all of Quebec

Date: Measures.

March 12, 2020: ban on indoor gatherings of more than 250 people.

March 13, 2020: declaration of a health emergency.

March 14, 2020: ban on non-essential visits to CHSLDs, hospitals and centers for the elderly; people aged 70 and over are asked to stay at home.

March 16, 2020: closure of educational establishments and daycare services; implementation of emergency childcare services; gradual closure of the Canadian border.

March 19, 2020: mandate to avoid travel between health regions.

March 21, 2020: ban on all indoor or outdoor gatherings.

March 28, 2020: **closure of 8 regions (Bas-Saint-Laurent, Abitibi-Témiscamingue, Côte-Nord, Saguenay-Lac-Saint-Jean, Gaspésie and Îles-de-la-Madeleine, Northern Quebec, Nunavik and Cree territory of James Bay).**

Beginning of April 2020: Gradual recovery of semi-urgent, then non-urgent operations.

April 5, 2020: closure of non-essential services.

April 6, 2020: start of online courses (CEGEPs).

April 15, 2020: opening of garages, mining sector, and landscaping activities.

April 20, 2020: reopening of construction and residential renovation.

April 21, 2020: closing of shopping centers, hair salons, beauty salons, etc.

April 29, 2020: Launch of MAVIPAN; arrival of the first military personnel in CHSLDs.

May 4, 2020: **opening of retail stores / stores with exterior door (excluding MMC); road checks withdrawn for certain regions (Chaudière-Appalaches, Lanaudière, Laurentides and the city of Rouyn-Noranda).**

May 6, 2020: authorization to go out for people living in private seniors' residences; certain visits now authorized.

May 11, 2020: **opening of primary schools and daycare services outside the MMC;** caregiver support authorized; healthy seniors start babysitting their grandchildren again (not an exact date); **road checks withdrawn for part of the Outaouais, Saguenay - Lac-Saint-Jean; Abitibi-Témiscamingue, La Tuque;** construction in civil engineering, infrastructure and commercial projects; manufacturing: 50 employees + 50% surplus employees per shift.

May 12, 2020: encouragement to wear a mask at all times outside the home.

May 18, 2020: **reopening of the following regions: Bas-Saint-Laurent, Gaspésie - Îles-de-la-Madeleine, Charlevoix.**

May 20, 2020: resumption of certain outdoor sports and individual leisure activities (e.g. golf and tennis).

May 22, 2020: right to outdoor gatherings of 10 people or less from a maximum of 3 households (distance of 2 m); certain rights granted to people with a disability or an Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

May 25, 2020: **opening of MMC retail businesses / stores with exterior door;** fully open factories (100% of employees).

May 29, 2020: opening of museums, libraries (loan counters) and drive-in movie theatres.

May 30, 2020: announcement of the opening of public outdoor swimming pools and play modules.

May 31, 2020: **reopening of a part of Côte-Nord.**

June 1, 2020: opening of professional and therapeutic health care (e.g., dentist), pet grooming; opening of personal and aesthetic care (e.g., hairdressers) outside MMC; opening of daycare services in the MMC and the MRC of Joliette; opening of retail centers outside MMC; opening of certain national parks and national historic sites; opening of campsites; gradual opening of courthouses; opening of marinas and certain categories of tourist accommodation establishments.

June 8, 2020: resumption of outdoor team sports (e.g., soccer, baseball) for practice only.

June 9, 2020: reopening of Jamésie, Terres-Cries-de-la-Baie-James and Nunavik.

June 15, 2020: opening of MMC hair salons, opening of restaurants (including buffets) outside MMC, Joliette and Épiphanie; indoor gatherings allowed for 10 people from a maximum of 3 households except for MMC, Joliette and Épiphanie.

June 22, 2020: opening of day camps (normal groups); indoor gatherings allowed for 10 people from a maximum of 3 households for MMC, Joliette and Épiphanie; opening of restaurants (including buffets) for MMC, Joliette and Épiphanie; indoor gatherings of 50 people or less in public places (except bars) permitted; reopening of beaches, indoor pools, gyms, arenas, cinemas and places of worship.

June 25, 2020: reopening of all sectors that were still confined (such as bars, spas, casinos, and water parks) except for festivals and major events, sleepover camps and combat sports.

July 13, 2020: masks mandatory in public transit.

July 18, 2020: masks mandatory in closed public places.

August 3, 2020: indoor and outdoor public gatherings of 250 people or less allowed.

August 24, 2020: masks mandatory for children 10 years old and over in public transit, school transit, indoor public places as well as outdoor ones that do not allow a physical distancing of 2 meters (therefore students must wear a mask at school from the fifth grade on, except while sitting in class).

September 16, 2020: Montreal, Montérégie, Bas-Saint-Laurent and Chaudière-Appalaches are designated yellow zones*.

September 20, 2020: Montreal, Capitale-Nationale and Chaudière-Appalaches are designated orange zones*.

September 29, 2020: The Greater Montréal Region, Capitale-Nationale, except Portneuf and Charlevoix, Chaudière-Appalaches and the MRC of La Rivière-du-Nord, in the Laurentides, are designated as red zones*.

October 1, 2020: The Laval region as well as the MRCs of Assomption and Moulins, in the Lanaudière region, move into the red zone. The Estrie, Bas-Saint-Laurent and Gaspésie are designated as orange zones*.

October 4, 2020: The municipalities of Maria, Carleton-sur-Mer and Nouvelle, in Gaspésie, are designated as red zones*.

October 11, 2020: Mauricie, Center-du-Québec, the city of Gatineau and the MRC des Collines-de-l'Outaouais, in the Outaouais region, are designated as red zones*.

October 13, 2020: Saguenay-Lac-Saint-Jean is designated as an orange zone*.

October 16, 2020: There are only five yellow zones* left in Quebec: Abitibi-Témiscamingue, Côte-Nord, Nord-de-Quebec, Terres-cries-de-la-Baie-James and Nunavik.

October 19, 2020: The MRCs of Joliette and Autray, in the Lanaudière region are designated as red zones*.

*Restrictive measures by zone as of October 1

Red zone

- Visitors from another address are prohibited, with a few exceptions (including the presence of a caregiver or someone offering a service, support, or planned work).
- Restaurant dining rooms and all bars are closed for 28 days, starting October 1. Delivery and take-out are still permitted.
- All cultural venues, including performance halls, cinemas, theaters, libraries, and museums are closed for 28 days as of October 1.
- Travel between regions is not recommended to green, yellow, or orange zones outside Quebec, with a few exceptions (including travel by workers, parents with shared custody of a child and truck drivers transporting goods).
- All businesses and boutiques remain open.
- Gyms, hair, and beauty salons remain open.
- Wearing a mask is mandatory during protests.
- In senior residences, such as CHSLDs, caregivers are welcome, but only one at a time, for a maximum of two people per day.
- Gatherings are prohibited, except in places of worship and funerals where they must be limited to 25 people; a registry must be kept.
- Health services in private practice, such as osteopathy or psychology, are maintained, if the care provided requires the presence of only one person.

Orange zone

- Private gatherings (indoor and outdoor) are limited to six people or two families, from no more than two residences.
- Maximum of 6 people per table in restaurants, bars, casinos, and gambling houses.
- Customers of bars, breweries, taverns, and casinos must leave the premises no later than midnight.
- Maximum of 25 people for indoor and outdoor activities (rented rooms, places of worship, celebratory events, weddings, etc.).
- In places with a liquor license, alcohol sales end at 11 p.m., no alcohol consumption after midnight and dancing activities prohibited.
- Maximum of 250 people in places where people are seated, relatively still and with little to no speaking (performance halls, cinemas, theaters, etc.).
- CHSLD visits are limited to humanitarian reasons or to caregivers providing significant help.
- Maximum of 6 people in apartments in private seniors' residences (RPA).
- Only one person per household in retail stores.
- Delivery services and help from relatives favoured for people at high risk of complications.
- Gyms may remain open, and sports activities remain permitted.
- Travel to other regions is not recommended.

Yellow zone

- Private gatherings (indoor and outdoor) are limited to 10 people.
- Maximum of 10 people per table in restaurants, bars, casinos, and gambling houses.
- Bars, breweries, taverns, and casinos open at 50% capacity, alcohol and food sale ending at midnight, closing at 1 a.m. and mandatory customer registry.
- Maximum of 50 people indoors (rented rooms, places of worship, celebratory events, weddings, etc.).
- In places with a liquor license, alcohol sales end at midnight, no alcohol consumption after 1 a.m. and dancing activities prohibited.
- Maximum of 250 people outdoors.
- Maximum of 250 people in places where people are seated, relatively still and with little to no speaking (performance halls, cinemas, theaters, etc.).
- Interregional travel authorized.

ANNEXE 3

Communications calendar

DATE	COMMUNICATION ACTION
AVRIL 29, 2020 (questionnaire published online)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No official release
AVRIL 30, 2020 (official start of recruitment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of the Facebook page • Dissemination in the personal/professional networks of the project team • Radio interview Jean-Pierre Després • Article in the Uval news • CIUSSS-CN news • Articles in the following newspapers: Le Charlevoisien, le Soleil, TVA Nouvelles,
MAY 1, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIHO Charlevoix radio info
MAY 3, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email Karine Latulippe in the Baie-St-Paul networks
MAY 4, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article from the Quebec Chief Scientist
MAY 5, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Messages to CIUSSS-CN employees
MAY 7, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIUSSS-CN newsletter
MAY 12, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication to Pulsar's mailing lists
MAY 13, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook publication of CISSS Côte-Nord • Publication of the study to Université Laval's mailing lists
MAY 13, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of Pulsar in the FIL of Université Laval
WEEK OF JUNE 01, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start of dissemination in the CISSS-CA
MAY 22, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview Marc-André Roy, Qub Radio
MAY 23, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAVIPAN Facebook post (English)
WEEK OF JUNE 28, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination by CIRRIS partners
JUNE 2 TO 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English Facebook push
JUNE 11, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radio-Canada Quebec interview